

D.5.2 – Report on Gender Perspectives into Energy-SHIFTS

WP5 – Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions

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<i>Abstract</i>	Report on the incorporation of a gender dimension into the 400 Energy-SHIFTS research priority questions through application of the Gender Innovation Approach (GIA). The aim was to demonstrate how implementing gender sensitive research may help achieve gender equality and justice in the context of energy transitions. The results show that the GIA was applicable to some 69% of all questions, with application being illustrated by published research in 38% of them. Gender remains to be mainstreamed into research on energy and energy transitions, but mainstreaming is imperative if research is to help advance gender equality in energy transitions.

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questions

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ACRONYMS

DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development
EU	European Union
EUA	European University Association
GIA	Gendered Innovations Approach
IC	Imperial College London
IRPPS	Italian National Research Council Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies
JU	Jagiellonian University in Kraków
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SET-PLAN	European Strategic Energy Technology Plan
SHIFTS	Social Sciences and Humanities Innovation Forum Targeting the SET-PLAN
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
WoS	Web of Science

1. INTRODUCTION

This document reports on the activities conducted for Task 5.2 in WP5 of the gEneSys project. The wider aims of gEneSys are to advance understanding of gender dimension in energy research, innovation, and socio-economic development to help accelerate the renewable energy transition and create more gender equitable and just sustainable energy solutions (gEneSys, 2024). gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a dynamic, gendered, mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem with technological, social, environmental, governance, and economic subsystems, each with its own sustainability visions, implementation concerns, power relations, values and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholders, yet linked so that events and changes in individual subsystem may also influence developments in other subsystems (Pollitzer, 2023).

Figure 1 gEneSys Conceptualisation of Energy Transition

The overarching aim of WP5 is to identify and address gender biases and gaps in evidence, analytical methods and knowledge that shape the discourse on equitable, just, and fair energy transition to develop credible energy transition pathways. These biases and gaps prevent women from having equality of opportunity with men to participate in, influence, and benefit from socio-technical transformations that enable and drive energy transitions (gEneSys, 2024).

Specifically, Task 5.2 aimed at addressing gender 'blindness' in the priority research questions proposed by the Energy SHIFTS project (Energy-SHIFTS, 2024). This entailed applying a Gendered Innovations Approach (GI, 2024) to the 400 Energy-SHIFTS questions, to demonstrate how implementing gender sensitive research may help

achieve gender equality and justice in the context of energy transitions. This task will also contribute inputs to other tasks in WP5, including the application of gender - integrated Energy-SHIFTS questions to the targets specified for SDG7 (i.e., ensuring access to clean and affordable energy; UN, 2024).

This report is structured as follows. It first introduces the Energy-SHIFTS project, its rationale and aims, before describing the role and features of the GIA (section 2). It then moves on to discuss the application of the GIA to the 400 Energy-SHIFTS priority research questions by the gEneSys research team (section 3). Next, the report introduces and discusses the key findings from integrating the GIA into the Energy-SHIFTS questions (section 4). The report concludes with final considerations on the effectiveness of GIA in helping redress the scant attention given to gender in research design on energy transitions (section 5).

2. ENERGY-SHIFTS AND THE GIA

2.1 The Energy-SHIFTS Project and SHIFTS Questions

The Horizon 2020 project *Energy Social Science and Humanities Innovation Forum Targeting the SET-Plan* (Energy-SHIFTS) was conducted to help inform and support EU-funded research and innovation to enable the achievement of climate neutrality in the EU by 2050 (Energy-SHIFTS, 2024). It emerged within the remit of the EU Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan) that aims to boost the transition towards a climate-neutral energy system through the swift development of cost-competitive low-carbon technologies (EC, 2024). Energy-SHIFTS was tasked with setting out priority Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research questions focused on energy to be considered for funding by the European Commission (EC) within the Horizon Europe research programme in a bid to widen opportunities for accessing funding for energy-related energy which has usually been taken up by the natural and technical sciences. Energy-SHIFTS formulated 100 research questions for each of four energy strands that fit in with existing EC research and innovation funding priorities and contribute to EU energy policy aims (Energy-SHIFTS, 2024). The strands and their mission statement are shown on Table 1.

Table 1 Energy-SHIFTS Strands and Mission

Strand	Mission Statement Orienting the Research Questions Design
Renewable Energy	To promote SSH research that contributes to better understanding the meaning and conditions of just transitions to renewables-based energy systems, by recognising the social conditions and consequences of using and further implementing renewable technologies (von Wirth, et al., 2020).
Smart Consumption	To demonstrate how SSH must play a leading role in smart energy transitions, in dialogue with technologists and policy makers, to accelerate a shift towards a sustainable energy future. To communicate that the social and technical aspects of smart cannot be separated, and the value of SSH in addressing challenging questions including those around values, justice, institutional change, democracy and participation. To reframe the smart consumption conversation, by highlighting how consumption is anchored in existing institutions and systems, which

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	means that transitions challenge power structures and vested interests (Robison, et al., 2020).
Energy Efficiency	To promote SSH research that better situates energy efficiency in relation to social systems of energy demand and supply; and to constructively challenge notions of energy efficiency by opening up questions of its meanings, applications and implications across diverse contexts, actors, and scales (Foulds, et al., 2020).
Transport and Mobility	To promote SSH research in the transition towards a carbon-neutral and socially just European transport system by 2050, which caters for human well-being, while acknowledging planetary boundaries and the need for climate change mitigation (Ryghaugh, et al., 2020).

The Energy-SHIFTS project team and scientific energy-SSH experts from across Europe convened in a Working Group (one for each strand) between 2019-October 2020 to carry out a Horizon Scanning exercise, part of a broad suite of Horizon scanning methods to “gain foresight about emerging opportunities and risks, identify knowledge gaps at the frontiers of fast-evolving phenomena, and set strategic priorities for decision-makers or researchers” (in von Wirth, et al., 2020). This entailed proposing research questions that were discussed and reviewed through a series of filtering steps that eventually produced the final set of 100 research priority questions divided into themes for each strand. Table 2 shows the numbered questions grouped into themes for each strand. It is worth noting that the ordering of themes does not imply their ranking and that themes may sometimes overlap to some extent. The priority research questions also aim to breach new perspectives that will engage researchers, funders, and policymakers in dialogue about how SSH evidence on the four strands can more effectively shore up transitions towards net zero carbon climate and more equitable and just societies (Energy-SHIFTS, 2024).

Table 2 Energy-SHIFTS: strands, themes and numbered questions

Strand: Renewable Energy¹		
N	Theme Title	Questions
1	Transformative governance	1-14
2	Culture, imaginaries, narratives	15-28
3	Social acceptance	29-34
4	Energy democracy	35-43
5	Energy Justice	44-53
6	Financial and organisational structure	54-58
7	Socio-ecological effects	59-65
8	Renewables policy	67-74
9	Renewables system design and integration across sectors	75-87
10	Geography of renewables	88-89
11	Power dynamics and conflicts	90-100
Strand: Smart Consumption²		
N	Theme Title	Questions
1	Power relations and smart energy transitions	1-12
2	Engagement and trust in relation to smart technology roll-out	13-26
3	Exclusion and unevenness in smart futures	27-37
4	Building communities for smart consumption and prosumption	38-51

5	How smart can become part of, or disrupt, everyday life	52-69
6	Beyond smart: evaluating assumptions and alternatives	70-84
7	Citizen, worker, parent: different roles involved in smart	85-100
Strand: Energy Efficiency³		
N	Theme Title	Questions
1	Citizenship, engagement, and knowledge exchange in relation to energy efficiency	1-14
2	Energy efficiency in relation to equity, justice, poverty, and vulnerability	15-30
3	Energy efficiency in relation to everyday life and practices of energy consumption and production	31-44
4	Framing, defining, and measuring energy efficiency	45-59
5	Governance, policy, and political issues around energy efficiency	60-74
6	Roles of economic systems, supply chains and financial mechanisms in improving energy efficiency	75- 86
7	The interactions, unintended consequences and rebound effects of energy efficiency interventions	87-100
Strand: Transport and Mobility⁴		
N	Theme Title	Questions
1	Co-producing knowledge and professional practices	1-15
2	Scenarios, futures, visions, and transition pathways	16-33
3	Dominant mobility regimes and car dependency	34-42
4	Governance, policies, and incentives	43-59
5	Participation and citizen engagement	60-65
6	Mobility practices and mobility needs	66-81
7	Risks, disruptions and negative or unanticipated consequences	82-90
8	Social justice and inclusion	91-100
Sources: ¹ (von Wirth, et al., 2020) ² (Robison, et al., 2020); ³ (Foulds, et al., 2020); ⁴ (Ryghaugh, et al., 2020)		

2.2 The Gendered Innovation Approach (GIA)

The GIA refers to a range of practical methods developed by the EU-Stanford University Gendered Innovations project to enable scientists and engineers to conduct sex, gender, and intersectional analysis in their research, and to provide case studies that concretely illustrate how such analysis leads to innovation, thereby 'stimulating gender-responsible science and technology that enhance the quality of life' for all genders around the world (GI, 2024).

The Gendered Innovations project has been developed and hosted at Stanford University since 2009. Over the 2010s it was joined by the US National Science Foundation (2012), and also informed the work of the Gendered Innovations Expert Group in the EU research programmes to help develop the gender dimension into EU research and innovation. Over the last few years, it has also widened its activities through international collaboration with experts from across the US and Canada, Europe, and Asia, leading to the updating and expansion of both sex, gender, and intersectional methods and case-studies (GI, 2024).

The gEneSys project aims to examine how approaches and understandings of energy transition processes can be made more sensitive to gender issues through use of GI (Pollitzer, 2023). gEneSys has adopted the GIA to test how it may support research on

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energy transition by placing gender issues at the forefront of energy transition processes, by:

- exploring how gender inequalities observed in existing energy systems may be overcome
- mainstreaming gender into new policy frameworks
- integrating a gender perspective into energy transition processes and outcomes
- advancing women in the energy ecosystem as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, leaders, employees, and consumers
- measuring and monitoring justice and fairness in energy transition outcomes
- promoting shared values of equity and sustainability
- responding to intersectional dimensions
- transforming power hierarchies
- facilitating societal acceptance of the changes (gEneSys, 2024).

As far as is known, the GIA has yet to be demonstrated in the context of energy transitions. Hence, Task 5.2 aims at highlighting the usefulness of incorporating the gender dimension into energy transitions research design and implementation through application of the GIA to each of the 400 Energy-SHIFTS research priority questions. Such application can in turn help enhance understanding of GI methodologies, and how they may be developed further. Table 3 shows the various GI methods and what they entail when applied to research on energy transitions. The numbering of the methodologies implies no ranking, being used solely for reference.

Table 3 GIA for Integrating Gender into Energy-SHIFTS Research Questions

1	Rethinking research priorities and outcomes considering whether gender differences are relevant; particularly important in the context of energy transition when assembling the evidence base to support analysis of individual subsystems and their interactions with one another
2	Rethinking concepts and theories unpicking definitions (e.g., “energy transition”) and clarifying understanding of the wording used when energy transition is debated (e.g., “just transition”; “energy poverty”) to help understand the influence of formal and informal social institutions, social norms, and gender stereotypes of human behaviour
3	Formulating research questions scoping the analytical approach to identify gender-related power hierarchies in energy systems (traditional and emerging); relevant gender questions include ‘how to ensure societal acceptance of radical innovations and understand impacts of environmental degradation of energy infrastructures on women’s livelihoods and health’
4	Analysing sex paying attention to essential, unchangeable biological differences and how they influence response to energy poverty, hunger, disease, or changes in environmental conditions (e.g., due to polluting household cooking equipment)
5	Analysing gender

understanding socio-cultural norms and stereotypes used in society to label an individual as male or female and recognising how socio-cultural differences and inequalities between women and men are maintained by social institutions

6 Analysing how sex and gender interact

combining biological and socio-cultural perspectives on the role and behaviours of women and men (e.g., tracking impact of greenhouse gas emissions may involve understanding the gendered nature of energy consumption as it relates to work, or within the household, and how it relates to health and wellbeing)

7 Intersectional approaches

paying attention to other human characteristics such as age, social status, education, ethnicity, race, geography, that play a role in defining vulnerability through lack of access to energy supply

8 Engineering Innovation Processes

creating socio-technical systems to ensure that energy transition pathways and low-carbon technologies do not propagate gender inequalities embedded in existing technologies (e.g., solar panels are particularly difficult to dismantle, which makes attempts to recycle the components very difficult, contributing to accumulation of electronic waste, but also restricting opportunities for creating employment for women in electronic waste processing sector)

9 Co-creation and Participatory Research

involving multiple actors and stakeholders in analysis of problems and generation of proposals for solutions, including the voices of rural, poor, indigenous, or other marginalised communities

10 Rethinking Standards and Reference Models

removing gender bias in energy transition where transparency and traceability in procurement of resources, products, and services is needed (e.g., to ensure availability and price of energy)

11 Rethinking Language and Visual Representations

demonstrating the gendered nature of energy transition in a way that can be easily comprehended by non-gender experts and lay persons (e.g., using images, graphics, stories when communicating rationales for gendered energy transitions)

Source: gEneSys (2024, adapted from GI, 2024)

A case-study of residential prosuming of solar energy in Norway and the UK (Standal, Talevi and Westskog, 2020) helps illustrate the application of GI methodologies to one specific piece of research on energy transition (Table 4).

Table 4 GIA application to case-study on residential solar prosuming in Norway and the UK

GI Methodology	Key descriptor	Addressed in the case-study Standal, Talevi and Westskog (2020)
1 Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes	highlighting relevance of gender differences	men more interested in rooftop solar power technology than women (uninterested/reluctant)
2 Rethinking Concepts and Theories	unpicking definitions	for some (men/women) becoming 'prosumers' was part of a process to assert themselves as environmentally friendly or energy savvy and engaging in other practices (using public transport; adapting energy consumption)

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3	<i>Formulating Research Questions</i>	identifying gender-related power hierarchies in energy systems	in Norway and UK men mostly took the initiative and put prosuming on the agenda in their home
4	<i>Analysing Sex</i>	highlighting role of biological differences on responses to energy systems/events/processes	both the gendered spaces of the household and the gendered division of labour within it influence how women and men interact with the technology adopted
5	<i>Analysing Gender</i>	highlighting role of socio-cultural norms and institutions in maintaining inequality between women and men	role of social practices and gender relations in 'residential prosuming'
6	<i>Analysing how Sex and Gender Interact</i>	identifying biological and socio-cultural perspectives on men and women's role and behaviour	gender division of labour in the home conditioned the different ways in which men and women prosumers generally interacted with solar PV technology
7	<i>Intersectional Approaches</i>	highlighting role of age, social status, education, ethnicity, race, and geography on access to energy	gender, age, class, ownership type, ethnicity, and language, may combine to thwart empowerment of citizens to manage their own energy consumption and contribute to sustainable supply of energy
8	<i>Engineering Innovation Processes</i>	avoiding reproduction of gender inequalities in novel socio-technical energy systems	social perception of prosuming as an exclusively male domain creates barriers to an inclusive decarbonised energy future
9	<i>Co-creation and Participatory Research</i>	involving multiple social actors in analysis of problems and generation of solutions	authors note the role of Norwegian Solar Association and UK Solar Energy Society in providing access to techno-economic information on solar energy
10	<i>Rethinking Standards and Reference Models</i>	removing gender bias in energy transition to ensure energy availability/affordability	women and men operate in different social fields (workplace, family, community group, neighbourhood) resulting in different dispositions and social positions that can affect their success as prosumers in solar energy
11	<i>Rethinking Language and Visual Representations</i>	making explicit the gendered nature of energy transition in ways accessible to non-gender experts/lay people	advertising and information material presented in ways that challenge the idea of prosuming and energy technology as male domains and appeal more to women

Sources: GI (2024); Standal, Talevi, & Westskog (2020)

3. APPLYING THE GIA TO THE ENERGY-SHIFTS QUESTIONS

3.1 Applying the GIA to the 400 Energy-SHIFTS Priority Research Questions

Members of the gEneSys' Consortium, comprising partners at ENEA, Fraunhofer, IC, IRPPS, JU and Portia, undertook the task of applying the GIA to the Energy-SHIFTS questions, working in sub-teams at each partner's institution. This firstly required developing a good understanding of the GIA methodologies as adapted to the context of energy (as summed up in Table 3) and of the Energy-SHIFTS project as regards the research questions, and on the latter, particularly awareness that out of

the 400 questions, only 11 explicitly refer to gender, as can be seen on Table 5 (emphasis added).

Table 5 The 11 Energy-SHIFTS Questions that Originally Address Gender out of all 400

Strand: Renewable Energy¹	
Number	Question
52	What are the key gaps in understanding the relation of gender equality with energy transitions (i.e., the shift to renewable energy)?
Strand: Smart Consumption²	
Number	Question
25	How can Social Sciences and Humanities insights help formulate smart consumption policies, e.g., within domains such as distributional challenges, gender equality, or to stimulate companies to use energy smarter?
94	In what ways does gender have an effect on private households' use of smart technologies; and how can gender perspectives be practically included in interventions and energy policy?
Strand: Energy Efficiency³	
Number	Question
16	To what extent can intersectional insights – regarding a person's social identities (e.g., gender , race, class, sexuality, religion, disability, etc.) – inform the design of energy efficiency solutions, and assist in devising strategies that address their unintended consequences?
21	How do energy efficiency improvements affect inequalities (including across e.g. socio-economic groups and genders); and how can policies be designed to achieve both energy efficiency and equity goals?
31	How do energy efficiency policies (e.g., energy pricing policies) affect everyday life for different groups, especially vulnerable groups, and different gender identities?
89	How does energy efficiency interact with other policy areas, such as urban planning, trade, gender , finance, labour policies, etc.; and in what ways can the promotion of other policy agendas conflict with energy efficiency goals?
Strand: Transport and Mobility⁴	
Number	Question
48	How can mobility policies be better integrated with policies from other sectors (e.g., energy efficiency, renewables, gender mainstreaming, poverty reduction)?
49	What policies could ensure that future mobility systems will be just and egalitarian, particularly with respect to gender , income, and ethnicity?
58	How can knowledge on gendered mobilities inform decision-making regarding sustainable urban mobility?
94	How can gender perspectives inform visions for inclusive and fair mobility; for example, how could systematic investigations of the gender inequalities embedded in current transport-energy systems help illuminate hidden injustices?
Sources: ¹ (von Wirth, et al., 2020); ² (Robison, et al., 2020); ³ (Foulds, et al., 2020); ⁴ (Ryghaugh, et al., 2020).	

The GI methodologies along with their description and all 400 priority research questions were set out in a database for the sub-teams to work on, with the research questions being divided among different sub-teams to achieve a balanced split. Next, each sub-team assessed each of its assigned questions to decide whether the topics addressed in the question necessitated the incorporation of a gender dimension through application of any of the GI methodologies. Given the explicit focus of the exercise on gender, a minimum requirement was the application of methodology 5 (*analysing gender*), and where appropriate, the application of any other methodologies.

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The last step in the exercise entailed demonstrating how the chosen methodologies help incorporate a gender dimension into the question. This entailed selecting at least one source of concrete evidence (i.e., a published research article) from the body of literature assembled and reviewed by the research team as part of other tasks in the gEneSys project (see section 3.2). This step required searching the reviewed literature database using keywords from the questions themselves to identify and read up on relevant research articles that illustrate one or more of the methodologies chosen as well as providing its online access link or the 'doi' address. The minimum criteria for selecting an article as evidence supporting the application of GIA methodologies was that it should address gender in a meaningful way, so that it was a recurrent issue in the paper (e.g., as a 'variable' in surveys; a 'category' in qualitative analysis; a central feature in case-studies, etc.). Table 6 summarises the steps as set out in the database file.

Table 6 Steps for Applying the GIA to Energy-SHIFTS questions

Energy-SHIFT question (theme/number)	Should gender be incorporated into this question? (yes/no)	What GIA methodologies are relevant? (number)	What piece of research demonstrates the application of these GIA methodologies to this question? (article title)	Source (online address)
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It was also expected that there might be cases where a research question should incorporate a gender dimension through assignation of any relevant GIA methodologies, even though no research article was available from the project's SLR database to demonstrate the application. These were noted down to highlight the need for drawing attention to gender issues in future research on energy and energy transition (discussed in section 4.1).

3.2 Applying the GIA into Energy-SHIFTS: the gEneSys SLR database

A key aim of the GIA is to enable scientists to carry out sex, gender, and intersectional analysis in their research to illustrate how such analysis contributes to the creation of innovation that helps address issues around gender equality and justice (GI, 2024). The application of the GIA to Energy-SHIFTS questions as reported here aimed at highlighting how a gender dimension can be meaningfully and usefully incorporated into them to produce novel knowledge that addresses gender equality and justice issues on research on energy and energy transitions. Clearly, the demonstration phase of the GIA into Energy-SHIFTS question was conducted retrospectively, drawing on the literature reviewed by gEneSys for a SLR that enables and supports various other tasks essential to the execution of the project (de Nicola, et al., 2023).

The SLR was carried out collaboratively by researchers across the gEneSys consortium which includes SSH researchers as well as researchers from the Science, Engineering and Technology fields. Working during the Spring of 2023, this team conducted searches using the Web of Science (WoS) to identify articles that addressed the nexus between gender and energy transition/transformation that were then selected for review. This process yielded a final literature database with 152 items covering the period 2000-2023, although two-thirds of the articles (98) were published between 2020-2023, and the remaining one third (54) was published between 2005-2019. The diverse articles examining the relations between gender and energy transition were organised into seven thematic clusters for analysis: 1) empowerment; 2) employment/work; 3) attitudes/behaviour; 4) transition to modern energy; 5) knowledge/awareness; 6) perception; and 7) health. The various findings of the SLR, include, for instance, the crucial need to understand how gender intersects with other social dimensions (e.g., race, ethnicity, age, education, class). However, it is to be noted that the themes of transport and mobility were not an explicit concern for inclusion in the SLR, and this has precluded the demonstration of the GIA application to questions on the Energy-SHIFTS 'Transport and Mobility' strand (discussed in section 4.1).

It is thus from this SLR database that research articles were selected to demonstrate how the GI methodologies apply to the 400 Energy-SHIFTS questions. Tables 7-11 illustrate the application of GIA to two questions selected from each theme in each of the four SHIFTS strands, one to which the GIA was applicable, and one where it was not. In the Tables 7-11, where only one question is shown with the answer in the positive in any one theme, this means that all questions on that theme were also answered in the positive and assigned GIA methodologies, and one research article is named to demonstrate the choice of methodologies for the question shown (i.e., Table 7: questions 41, 46; Table 8: questions 3, 14, 28, 48; Table 9: question 84; Table 10: questions 17, 62).

Conversely, where only one question is shown with the answer in the negative in any one theme, this means that all questions on that theme were also answered in the negative, so no GIA methodologies were assigned and consequently, no demonstration was required (Table 7: questions 80 and 88). On several occasions too, more than one article was found to demonstrate the GIA applied to any one question and, conversely, one same article could also help demonstrate the GIA to more than one question.

Clearly, a limitation of testing the applicability of GIA in research on energy transition as discussed here is the use of the 152 studies identified through the methodology employed for the SLR, which considered as the source the literature available through WoS.

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Table 7 Applying the GIA to SHIFTS Renewable Energy (1)

Applying the GIA to the SHIFTS Questions									
Strand: Renewable Energy (1)									
Theme	1 Transformative governance	2 Cultural imaginaries narratives		3 Social acceptance		4 Energy democracy	5 Energy justice	6 Financial and organisational structures	
Question Number	3	17	26	29	34	41	46	56	58
SHIFT question	What is the role of disruptive events as potential game changers in transitions to renewable energy sources?	What challenges and opportunities do left/ right populist politics pose for renewable energy uptake in Europe?	What are the emerging identities associated with renewables?	Which factors influence the perception of renewables among citizens?	How can the social acceptance in cross-national cooperation for renewable energy in Europe be increased?	What tools and methods offered by SSH are useful for participatory governance of renewables?	How is it possible to avoid or to reduce energy injustice?	What are the factors influencing people's willingness to invest in small-scale renewables?	Which new collective investment approaches might enable renewable energy transitions on a large-scale across nation states? for example, what might the potential be of a global financial transaction tax or a global renewables investment trust?
Add GIA?	yes	no	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no
GIA	2, 5, 8, 10		5,7,10	2, 5, 10		2,5,7,10	2,5,10	5	
Research Article (Title)	Disruptive innovation for inclusive renewable policy in sub-Saharan Africa: a social shaping of technology analysis of appliance uptake in Rwanda		Sustainable energy for all or sustainable energy for men? Gender and the construction of identity within climate technology entrepreneurship in Kenya	Perceptions of participation and the role of gender for the engagement in solar energy communities in Sweden		Patriarchy and (electric) power? A feminist political ecology of solar energy use in Mexico and the United States	Women's leadership in renewable transformation, energy justice and energy democracy: redistributing power	Engaging men and women in energy production in Norway and the United Kingdom: the significance of social practices and gender relations	
Available at:	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.12.091		http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.05.059	http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13705-021-00312-6		http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101743	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101233	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338	

Table 8 Applying the GIA to SHIFTS Renewable Energy (2)

Applying the GIA to the SHIFTS Questions								
Strand: Renewable Energy (2)								
Theme	7 Socio-ecological effects		8 Renewables policy		9 Renewables system design and integration across sectors	10 Geography of renewables	11 Power dynamics and conflicts	
Question Number	60	63	66	71	80	88	91	100
SHIFT question	How can renewable energy deployment be increased without creating negative impacts on biodiversity?	What are the negative and positive impacts of renewables on landscape (with respect to human quality of life)?	Which policies on renewable energy need to be designed in order to reach the EU 2050 carbon-neutrality goal?	How can policies at different government levels (e.g. European, national, regional and local) reinforce each other, in increasing community acceptance of renewable energy projects?	How can transitions to renewable energy technologies be combined with shifting to a circular economy?	What are the most effective and efficient scenarios of reaching 100% renewable energy in different EU Member States?	Under what conditions does societal support for renewable energy translate, or not, into political action?	How can powerful fossil fuel actors and interests be involved in transitions towards renewable energy systems?
Add GIA?	no	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes	no
GIA		3,4,5	4,5,6				3,5	
Research Article (Title)		The Health Impact of Household Cooking Fuel Choice on Women: Evidence from China	Consumers' Willingness to Pay for the Solar Photovoltaic System in the Post-Subsidy Era: A Comparative Analysis under an Urban-Rural Divide				The effect of women's parliamentary participation on renewable energy policy outcomes	
Available at:		https://doi.org/10.3390/su132112080	https://doi.org/10.3390/en15239022				https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12539	

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Table 9 Applying the GIA to SHIFTS Smart Consumption

Applying the GIA to the SHIFTS Questions										
Strand: Smart Consumption										
Theme	1 Power relations and smart energy transitions	2 Engagement and trust in relation to smart technology roll-out	3 Exclusion and unevenness in smart futures	4 Building communities for smart consumption and prosumption	5 How smart can become part of, or disrupt, everyday life		6 Beyond smart: evaluating assumptions and alternatives		7 Citizen, worker, parent: different roles involved in smart	
Question Number	3	14	28	48	55	66	82	84	92	97
SHIFT question	Which gaps exist between energy governance and digital governance systems; and how are these affecting the development of smart, low-carbon consumption?	How do the uses of smart technologies (and their associated socio-technical energy systems) affect relations of trust?	How can smart technology initiatives engage citizens from socio-economic classes associated with higher carbon emissions, in order to lower emissions?	What are the roles of different technology user groups and actors in efforts to successfully upscale from local pilots, experiments and bottom-up initiatives within the area of smart consumption?	What are the prospects of Home Energy Management as a social practice?	How could the use of smart technologies help countries prepare for a major and potentially controversial transition to electromobility?	How can smart technologies enable sufficiency-based practices, activities and simple living to become (more) conceivable, enabled and satisfying, in order to realise essential carbon savings?	How do discourses of smart consumption interplay with alternative discourses (e.g. around degrowth, technological sovereignty etc.)?	How could participation within and across networks of communities facilitate learning of new, smart energy consumption practices?	What are the barriers for network operators (e.g. legal, economic, regulatory etc.) who want to introduce smart consumption options for their customers?
Add GIA?	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no
GIA	5	5,9	5	5	5		1,2,3,5,7,8		5,7	
Research Article (Title)	Does board gender diversity affect renewable energy consumption?	Advancing Households' Sustainable Energy through Gender Attitudes towards Rooftop PV Installations: A Case of the Central Highlands, Vietnam	Illuminant intersections: Injustice and inequality through electricity and water infrastructures at the Gujarat Solar Park in India	Patriarchy and (electric) power? A feminist political ecology of solar energy use in Mexico and the United States	Social impacts of large-scale solar thermal power plants: Assessment results for the NOORO I		Changing energy geographies: The political effects of a small-scale electrification project		Energy 4 all? Investigating gendered energy justice implications of community-based micro-hydropower cooperatives in Ethiopia	
Available at:	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2020.101665	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13020942	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102309	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101743	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338		http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2018.09.016		http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2020.1745059	

Table 10 Applying the GIA to SHIFTS Energy Efficiency

Applying the GIA to the SHIFTS Questions													
Strand: Energy Efficiency													
Theme	1 Citizenship, engagement and knowledge exchange in relation to energy efficiency		2 Energy efficiency in relation to equity, justice, poverty and vulnerability		3 Energy efficiency in relation to everyday life and practices of energy consumption and production		4 Framing, defining and measuring energy efficiency		5 Governance, policy and political issues around energy efficiency		6 Roles of economic systems, supply chains and financial mechanisms in improving energy efficiency	7 The interactions, unintended consequences and rebound effects of energy efficiency interventions	
Question Number	5	4	18	19	33	44	46	49	60	69	84	89	99
SHIFT question	How can 'real laboratories' – such as urban experiments that co-design, carry out, observe and evaluate complex social change processes – contribute to energy transitions?	What social and procedural components need to be considered in establishing community-based energy efficiency projects; and how can these considerations be most effectively incorporated into project design and implementation?	To what extent do existing energy efficiency policies, tools and initiatives employ a social justice approach; what would be the implications of embedding a social justice approach throughout policymaking on energy efficiency; and how can this best be achieved?	How does a fair distribution of energy efficiency costs and benefits feature in societies' idea of acceptability; including, what exactly does 'fair' mean to different stakeholders?	What are the emerging (disruptive) energy efficiency technologies that might significantly transform the ways people live and work?	What are the conditions that facilitate the acceptance and pursuit of energy sufficiency (e.g. living in smaller spaces, avoiding mobility, reducing consumption) over energy efficiency; and how can these conditions be scaled-up across society?	How is the making of energy efficiency policies influenced by forecasts, models, imaginaries and visions of energy supply and energy demand?	How do political and institutional contexts shape the ways in which energy efficiency is defined and measured; and how do these contexts determine who has authority in these processes of classification and quantification?	60 What role can policy instruments play in advancing energy efficiency and sufficiency in different fields, such as 'deep renovation' of buildings, product policy, or digital infrastructures; and how do existing policy instruments perform on efficiency and actual energy savings?	Which geo-political factors play important roles in facilitating international cooperation for enhancing energy efficiency policies?	What new models and mechanisms for sharing, trading and accounting for energy resources are emerging; and what might these socio-economic innovations mean for energy efficiency and energy sufficiency?	How does energy efficiency interact with other policy areas, such as urban planning, trade, gender, finance, labour policies, etc.; and in what ways can the promotion of other policy agendas conflict with energy efficiency goals?	How do different forms of maintenance - for example, processes for monitoring, repairing and upgrading infrastructures - shape energy efficiency outcomes over long timescales?
Add GIA?	no	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	no
GIA		5, 7, 9	5,7			5,7		5	3, 4,5,6,7,9, 10		1,2,5,8	5, 6,7,10	
Research Article (Title)		Local Aspects of UK Renewable Energy Development: Exploring Public Beliefs and Policy Implications	Technology, Gender, and Climate Change: A Feminist Examination of Climate Technologies			Social Acceptance of Wind Energy in Urban Landscapes		The effect of women's parliamentary participation on renewable energy policy outcomes	Canada's Green New Deal: Forging the socio-political foundations of climate resilient infrastructure?		Toward feminist energy systems: Why adding women and solar panels is not enough	Towards a Systemic Assessment of Gendered Energy Transition in Urban Households	
Available at:		http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/1354983042000309315	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/soc8040109			http://dx.doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1389		http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12539	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101442	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101557	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101557	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en14217251	

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Table 11 Applying the GIA SHIFTS Transport and Mobility

Applying the GIA to the SHIFTS Questions														
Strand: Transport and Mobility														
Theme	1 Co-producing knowledge and professional practices		2 Scenarios, futures, visions and transition pathways	3 Dominant mobility regime and car dependency		4 Governance, policy and incentives		5 Participation and citizen engagement	6 Mobility practice and mobility needs		7 Risks, disruptions and negative or unanticipated consequences		8 Social justice and inclusion	
Question Number	3	4	17	36	41	48	49	62	76	79	82	85	94	100
SHIFT question	What theoretical and policy tools are needed to better attend to rural and smalltown geographies, in both the Global South and the Global North, in envisioning inclusive and sustainable mobility futures?	How can transport research, policy and planning be better integrated with social science and ethical considerations, to ensure that the implementation of greener transport solutions do not increase injustices and to ensure accessibility for all users?	How should future mobility be organised in post-fossil fuel cities?	How can a modal shift be achieved, from energy-consuming mobility modes towards more sustainable modes; and what may be the most appropriate governance solutions for especially rapidly motorising countries (in e.g. Eastern Europe)?	How may shared-mobility services be used to reduce the dominance of private car ownership?	How can mobility policies be better integrated with policies from other sectors (e.g. energy efficiency, renewables, gender mainstreaming, poverty reduction)?	What policies could ensure that future mobility systems will be just and egalitarian, particularly with respect to gender, income and ethnicity?	How can residents' opinions and priorities be better integrated into mobility planning?	How can users' sensory and emotional experiences with different transport technologies and mobility practices better inform efforts to change mobility habits?	How may barriers to disrupting transport system lock-ins, which are produced by industry complexes and decision-makers outside the transport domain (e.g. CEOs and policy-makers related to all industries), be addressed?	What are the main unintended consequences of new low-carbon transport technologies; and how can undesirable effects be minimised?	Will automatisation and enhanced connectivity widen or narrow existing spatial differences and social inequalities; and how may this vary (or not) between/within different countries, regions, and urban and rural areas?	How can gender perspectives inform visions for inclusive and fair mobility; for example, how could systematic investigations of the gender inequalities embedded in current transport-energy systems help illuminate hidden injustices?	How should transport systems be organised to meet the mobility needs of those who, for various reasons, do not have (access to) a car; and how can transport systems in car-free cities be organised?
Add GIA?	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	no	yes	yes
GIA	5,6,7		5,7		5,7,8		5,6,7	5, 9, 10, 11	1, 4, 5, 7,		5,8		1,2,3,5,7	1,2,3,5,7,9
Research Article (Title)	none		none		none		none	none	none		none		none	none

4. GENDER INTO THE ENERGY-SHIFTS QUESTIONS

4.1 Incorporating Gender into the Energy-SHIFTS questions

The exercise of applying GIA methodologies to the 400 Energy-SHIFTS priority research questions revealed that the GIA was applicable to many questions and demonstrated in many cases too. Table 12 shows the outcomes of the exercise, noting the number of questions for each theme in each strand that should incorporate gender and that can be demonstrated by a published research article available from the gEneSys SLR database. Demonstration was highest for questions in Smart Consumption (N=72), and high for questions in Renewable Energy (N=59), but low for questions in Energy Efficiency (N=21). No demonstration was possible for Transport and Mobility because, as noted earlier, these were not a central theme in the gEneSys SLR and no research articles addressing these themes were available in the SLR database. In total, the GIA application could be demonstrated for 38% of all 400 priority research questions, although the GIA was applicable to some 69% of all questions when including those questions that could not be demonstrated by any article from the SLR database but could be connected to studies with which the gEneSys team was familiar.

Table 12 Incorporating the GIA into Energy-SHIFTS research questions with evidence

Strand	Theme and Number	Questions	GIA applied	With evidence
Renewable Energy	1 Transformative governance	14	14	all
	2 Cultural imaginaries narratives	14	10	all
	3 Social acceptance	6	5	all
	4 Energy democracy	9	9	all
	5 Energy justice	10	9	all
	6 Financial and organisational structures	5	4	all
	7 Socio-ecological effects	7	3	all
	8 Renewables policy	9	3	all
	9 Renewables system design and integration across sectors	13	none	n/a
	10 Geography of renewables	2	none	n/a
	11 Power dynamics and conflicts	11	2	all
Strand	Theme and Number	Questions	GIA applied	With evidence
Smart Consumption	1 Power relations and smart energy transitions	12	12	10
	2 Engagement and trust in relation to smart technology roll-out	5	4	all
	3 Exclusion and unevenness in smart futures	11	11	all
	4 Building communities for smart consumption and prosumption	14	14	all
	5 How smart can become part of, or disrupt, everyday life	18	14	all
	6 Beyond smart: evaluating assumptions and alternatives	15	7	all
	7 Citizen, worker, parent: different roles involved in smart	16	13	12
Strand	Theme and Number	Questions	GIA applied	With evidence
Energy Efficiency	1 Citizenship, engagement, and knowledge in relation to energy efficiency	14	12	4
	2 Energy efficiency in relation to equity, justice, poverty, and vulnerability	16	12	4

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	3 Energy efficiency in relation to everyday life and practices of energy consumption and production	14	8	2
	4 Framing, defining, and measuring energy efficiency	15	1	1
	5 Governance, policy, and political issues around energy efficiency	15	13	4
	6 Roles of economic systems, supply chains and financial mechanisms in improving energy efficiency	12	12	5
	7 The interactions, unintended consequences and rebound effects of energy efficiency interventions	14	12	1
Strand	Theme and Number	Questions	GIA applied	With evidence
Transport and Mobility	1 Co-producing knowledge and professional practices	15	11	none
	2 Scenarios, futures, visions, and transition pathways	18	18	none
	3 Dominant mobility regimes and car dependency	9	7	none
	4 Governance, policies, and incentives	17	7	none
	5 Participation and citizen engagement	6	6	none
	6 Mobility practices and mobility needs	16	16	none
	7 Risks, disruptions and negative or unanticipated consequences	9	3	none
	8 Social justice and inclusion	10	2	none
Source: compiled by the authors based on GI (2024) and Energy-SHIFTS (2024)				

Demonstration of gender incorporation into Energy-SHIFTS questions did not necessarily entail a complete fit between the topics addressed in any one question, the GIA methodologies applied, and the aims and goals of the research reported in the demonstrating article. For the most part, the articles in the SLR database made no explicit reference to the GIA-related methodologies as described here, although clearly many did employ concepts and theories relevant to the gender-energy nexus that orient the gEneSys project (e.g., feminist approaches). Demonstration was predicated on establishing that the reported research addressed or illuminated central aspects of the GIA methodologies chosen, regardless of whether such aspects were ever envisaged or examined in the research in the first place (e.g., socio-demographic characteristics enabling intersectional analysis). For instance, articles might often discuss the gender implications of energy-related interventions for gender - whether positive or negative outcomes or a mix of both- thus helping highlight the usefulness of examining them through a specific GIA methodology. Table 13 shows the articles that demonstrate the GIA methodologies applied to questions across the strands that include gender in the title. They illustrate the breadth of topics addressed by research on the gender-energy nexus that correlates to topics included in Energy-SHIFTS questions

Table 13 Gender in the title: incorporation gender into Energy-SHIFTS questions

Q	Title	GIA	DOI
Strand: Renewable Energy			
6	Engaging men and women in energy production in Norway and the United Kingdom: The significance of social practices and gender relations	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338
12	Three sides to every story: Gender perspectives in energy transition pathways in Canada, Kenya and Spain	1,2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101550
15	Rethinking education for SDG 7: A framework for embedding gender and critical skills in energy access masters' programmes in Africa	1,2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102615
16	The trade-off between gender, energy and climate change in Africa: the case of Niger Republic	5,2,10	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-020-10246-9
19	Cultural norms to support gender equity in energy development: Grounding the productive use agenda in Rwanda	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102543
21	The Anti-Politics Machine of Green Energy Development: The Moroccan Solar Project in Ouarzazate and Its Impact on Gendered Local Communities	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/land8060100
26	Sustainable energy for all or sustainable energy for men? Gender and the construction of identity within climate technology entrepreneurship in Kenya	5,7,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1464993416688830
27	Rethinking education for SDG 7: A framework for embedding gender and critical skills in energy access masters programmes in Africa	5,7,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102615
29	Perceptions of participation and the role of gender for the engagement in solar energy communities in Sweden	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13705-021-00312-6
31	Preferences for energy sustainability: Different effects of gender on knowledge and importance	5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110767
39	Energy 4 all? Investigating gendered energy justice implications of community-based micro-hydropower cooperatives in Ethiopia	1,5	http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2020.1745059
42	A Heat Pump Needs a Bit of Care: On Maintainability and Repairing Gender-Technology Relations	2,5,6, 10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0162243920978301
44	Evidence of multidimensional gender inequality in energy services from a large-scale household survey in India	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41560-022-01044-3
45	The rise of solar home systems in sub-Saharan Africa: Examining gender, class, and sustainability	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102011
47	Gender audits: An approach to engendering energy policy in Nepal, Kenya and Senegal	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101378
50	Rural energy profiles and the role of solar energy in climate change mitigation - a gendered perspective	2,5,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10130950.2014.932163
52	Closing the renewable energy gender gap in the United States and Canada: The role of women's professional networking	2,5,11	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.03.011
94	Does board gender diversity affect renewable energy consumption?	3,5	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2020.101665
Strand: Smart Consumption			
7	Cultural norms to support gender equity in energy development: Grounding the productive use agenda in Rwanda	5	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102543
14	Advancing Households' Sustainable Energy through Gender Attitudes towards Rooftop PV Installations: A Case of the Central Highlands, Vietnam	5,9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13020942
37	Gender and ethnic disparities in energy poverty: The case of South Africa	5,3	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112755
45	Sustainable Development, Energy Transition, and Climate Challenges in the Context of Gender: The Framework of Gender Determinants of Environmental Orientation in Poland	5	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su12219214
50	The need for gender-based approach in the assessment of local energy projects [Spain/Greece]	5	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2022.03.001
56	Coal reliance, human development, and gender equality: At what scale should we look for a relationship?	5,7,8,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102612
75	Breaking the Dichotomies: Climate, Coal, and Gender. Paving the Way to a Just Transition. The Example of Colombia	1,2,3,5,8	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en14175457
77	Bright as night: Illuminating the antinomies of 'gender positive' solar development	1,2,3,5,7,9	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105196
90	Gender matters: Women, renewable energy, and citizen participation in Germany	5,7	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.02.005
93	Energy, equality and sustainability? European electricity cooperatives from a gender perspective	5,7	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101247
95	Examining the Gender Dynamics of Green Grabbing and Ejido Privatization in Zacatecas, Mexico	1,2,3	http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.657413
Strand: Energy Efficiency			
18	Technology, Gender, and Climate Change: A Feminist Examination of Climate Technologies	5,7	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/soc8040109
49	Gender, electricity access, renewable energy consumption and energy efficiency	5	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121121
83	Embedding gender factor in energy input-output analysis of paddy production systems in Mazandaran Province, Iran	5,6,7,11	http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40974-017-0054-y
89	Towards a Systemic Assessment of Gendered Energy Transition in Urban Households	6,7,10	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en14217251

Sources: author's compilation based on GI (2024) and Energy-SHIFTS (2024)

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questions

The demonstration of the GIA into the Energy-SHIFTS questions is made directly by the case-study introduced earlier on residential prosuming in Norway and in the UK (section 2.2). This paper helps illustrate the application of GIA to questions across three strands (12 questions in total, encompassing six GI methodologies), as shown on Table 14.

Table 14 Case-study demonstrating the application of GIA into Energy-SHIFTS questions

Source: Standal, Talevi and Westskog (2020); (doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338) 'Engaging men and women in energy production in Norway and the United Kingdom: the significance of social practices and gender relations' (the experiences of prosumer households on adopting residential solar energy systems)			
N	Question	GIA	Relevant key issues examined/revealed in the article
Strand: Renewable Energy			
5	What are the effective measures of engaging citizens in generating, conserving and distributing energy differently?	2,5,10	environmental, economic and technological benefits as motivators for investing in a rooftop solar system (men more interested in technology; women uninterested/reliant)
56	What are the factors influencing people's willingness to invest in small-scale renewables?	5	role of social practices and gender relations in 'residential prosuming' (producing own energy and selling excess to the grid)
Strand: Smart Consumption			
13	In what ways do the introduction and use of emergent smart energy technologies create new means of engagement in wider energy and climate issues; and what are the impacts of this engagement?	5,9	for some (men/women alike) becoming prosumers was part of a process to assert themselves as environmentally friendly or energy savvy and engaging in other practices such as using public transport; several had rescheduled their electricity consumption to fit with the periods that were optimal for the solar system to produce electricity; felt responsible for decreasing their energy consumption in order to live more environmentally sustainable lives and prosuming as personal contribution to nationwide/global effort to mitigate climate change
20	In what ways are different combinations of economic and non-economic incentives effective in encouraging a socio-technical energy system that includes smart consumption?	5	environmental, economic and technological benefits as motivators for investing in a rooftop solar system (men more interested in technology; women uninterested/reliant to engage)
21	What are the relationships between citizens' energy literacy* (i.e., knowledge about key energy issues of relevance to everyday life) and effective public engagement in smart consumption and energy transitions?	5,11	in Norway, men with technological interests or people working in the energy sector benefitted from their understanding of prosuming and from the availability of information and suppliers; in Norway and UK men mostly took the initiative and put prosuming on the agenda in their home
22	How can understandings of smart consumption be integrated into modern education practices?	5,11	by paying attention to gender aspects and social differentiation in general when designing support schemes for PV systems, information material and campaigns, marketing activities for home solar systems, policymakers, associations and companies can frame prosuming in ways that appeal both to those who are tech-savvy and to those who are not; advertising and information material can be presented in ways that challenge the idea of prosuming and energy technology as male domains and thereby appeal more to women
23	What is the interplay between community acceptance and market acceptance ambitions (of developers or policymakers) related to smart technologies, and the level of agency therefore afforded to users; and how can agency be maintained?	5,7	need for policies to be designed to promote new practices that are inclusive and that appeal to a more diverse group to transition to a more sustainable and equitable low-carbon energy system; the gender difference in skills, social networks and financial capital resulted in reduced agency for some women; women did not get equally involved in installation of solar Photovoltaic system as their contribution was not needed (partners drove the process)
39	How can the socio-technical system of power supply move away from centralisation, to be transformed into a smarter system where energy may be co-produced and consumed as a common good (e.g., as managed by prosumer* communities)?	5	gender, age, class, ownership type, ethnicity and language, further thwart the realisation of a scenario where citizens are empowered to become managers of their energy consumption and contributors to the sustainable supply of energy
40	What are the drivers that enable certain groups of energy users to act together and develop collective solutions for smart consumption and prosuming; and what are the institutional lock-in factors obstructing this?	5	Norwegian Solar association (member-based civil society organisation) promotes solar energy and represents industry and consumers; UK Solar Energy Society represents industry and the public
41	What are the potential roles of prosumers in the transition towards a system with active smart users instead of passive consumers; and how can institutional conditions better enable this?	5	engagement in household solar systems is gendered (i.e., women and men with different economic, social, cultural capital) and influences interaction with technology in the transition from consumers to prosumers; gender division of labour in the home conditioned the different ways in which men and women prosumers generally interacted with solar PV technology
48	What are the roles of different technology user groups and actors in efforts to successfully upscale from local pilots, experiments and bottom-up initiatives within the area of smart consumption?	5	women and men operate in different social fields (workplace, family, community group, neighbourhood) resulting in different dispositions and social positions that can affect their success as prosumers; in context of residential PV solar energy production/consumption, men deal with much of the prosumer-related issues while women perform the traditional energy-consuming tasks
Strand: Energy Efficiency			
6	What are the challenges to mobilising collective action around energy efficiency and sufficiency (e.g., convincing private apartment owners to undertake collective refurbishments); and what learnings on addressing these can be drawn from exemplars?	3,5	the need for financial capital in the form of one's own house (with the right roof type and orientation) and money to invest; women tend to have less of the economic, cultural and social capitals needed to become prosumers, whereas men are more often associated with the cultural and symbolic capitals that frame technology as largely a male domain; if prosuming is socially perceived as an exclusively male domain, it creates barriers to an inclusive decarbonised energy future; removing barriers will require recruiting women into STEM education and occupations, which is needed to achieve an equitable and sustainable energy transition; measures needed to enhance energy literacy and awareness in general population to ensure that people (men/women) realise the importance of energy transition and energy efficiency
Source: authors' compilation based on Energy-SHIFTS (2024) and GI (2024).			

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As noted earlier too, the application of the GIA was seen as relevant to various other Energy-SHIFTS questions even though no sources from the gEneSys SLR database could be used for demonstration. Table 15 shows a selection of such questions for each theme on each strand, to give a sense of types of topics addressed.

Table 15 The GIA into Energy-SHIFTS research questions that require demonstration

Strand: Smart Consumption¹	
Theme	Question
1 Power relations and smart energy transitions	1. What is the nature and scale of abusive use of smart technology; and what actions could be taken to reduce this?
7 Citizen, worker, parent: different roles involved in smart	86. How does the notion of 'smart consumers' (e.g., in EU policy discourses) change the modern understanding of citizenship?
Strand: Energy Efficiency²	
Theme	Question
1 Citizenship, engagement, and knowledge exchange in relation to energy efficiency	13. How can policies and public programmes aiming to increase energy efficiency, via citizen engagement, go beyond individualistic models of behaviour; and how can a social practice frame result in different types of programmes?
2 Energy efficiency in relation to equity, justice, poverty, and vulnerability	23. What roles do material culture and interactions with technologies play in shaping the distributional inequalities experienced through different energy efficiency initiatives?
3 Energy efficiency in relation to everyday life and practices of energy consumption and production	37. What unanticipated challenges and poor outcomes arise from a lack of 'fit' between new initiatives or technologies with everyday lives and practices; and how can these be addressed?
5 Governance, policy and political issues around energy efficiency	68. What is the role of intermediary organisations in creating an 'entrepreneurial ecosystem'; and what kinds of organisational ecosystem governance can help scale up energy efficiency innovations?
6 Roles of economic systems, supply chains and financial mechanisms in improving energy efficiency	86. How could alternative economic systems (e.g., slow, local, time-rich, high satisfaction economies) contribute to energy efficiency and energy sufficiency?
7 The interactions, unintended consequences and rebound effects of energy efficiency interventions	97. What are the relationships between energy efficiency, energy demand and human well-being; and what roles could energy efficiency and energy sufficiency play in policy interventions to tackle inequalities in well-being?
Strand: Transport and Mobility³	
Theme	Question
1 Co-producing knowledge and professional practices	5. How can more inclusive mechanisms and approaches that co-produce research and policy making be developed, to not only include technocrats, but also other equally important voices (e.g., citizens, vulnerable groups, SSH researchers)?
2 Scenarios, futures, visions, and transition pathways	24. What social, cultural, and political factors need consideration in the development of neighbourhood vehicle sharing systems?
3 Dominant mobility regimes and car dependency	40. What are the main factors contributing to attitude changes among people in countries where motorisation is still growing?
4 Governance, policies, and incentives	45. What policy tools are most effective in supporting increased cycling and walking in cities?
5 Participation and citizen engagement	65. What engagement methods and approaches are most appropriate in generating citizen-led visions of mobility futures; and specifically, what would a reduced-car or car-free city in such visions mean to citizens?
6 Mobility practices and mobility needs	66. To what extent can more sustainable forms of transport and mobility increase human well-being?
7 Risks, disruptions and negative or unanticipated consequences	86. To what extent do social attitudes surrounding privacy pose a challenge for the acceptability of shared-mobility practices?
8 Social justice and inclusion	98. In what ways are policies aiming to achieve sustainable transport and avoid car dependence (e.g., congestion pricing, low-emission areas) deepening transport-related inequalities?

Sources: ¹ (Robison, et al., 2020); ² (Foulds, et al., 2020); ³ (Ryghaugh, et al., 2020).

4.2 GIA not relevant or required for some Energy-SHIFTS questions

The GIA was not seen to be applicable to several of the Energy-SHIFTS research questions. This might be because, on the one hand, the topics addressed in these questions obviated the need for making explicit the gender dimension (i.e., gender is implied or subsumed in the question). On the other hand, it might be because the topic, scope or geographical scale covered in the questions did not lend these to meaningful application of GIA methodologies. A sample of these questions is shown on Tables 7-11 covering the relevant themes across the four strands.

5. ENERGY-SHIFTS FOR GENDER EQUALITY

The application of GIA to the Energy-SHIFTS priority research questions and demonstration with extant research evidence aimed at highlighting the need and usefulness of incorporating gender dimensions explicitly into research on energy, energy systems and energy transitions - as in research advocated by the Energy-SHIFTS project. As far as it is known, this was the first time that the GIA was used in the context of energy research design.

The application of GIA to the Energy-SHIFTS priority research questions was not exhaustive since, clearly, it is possible to explore further a great variety of triangulations of GI methodologies with the research questions and demonstrating articles. Yet, those that were examined here clearly helped achieve the aim of testing the usefulness of GIA in identifying gender biases in study design and in the expected quality of research outcomes.

The exercise was supported by the gEneSys SLR database, which is comprehensive, although focused on specific aspects of the gender-energy nexus examined in the gEneSys project. The range of such aspect is likely set to expand in coming years, given the increasing importance of gender in energy and energy transitions research. For instance, questions in the Transport and Mobility strand could not be demonstrated because these two themes were not central concerns guiding the gEneSys SLR. Yet, as shown, the GIA was applicable to most questions on this strand, thereby highlighting their relevance and importance to research in the gender-energy nexus. Recent literature searches suggest that research on the linkages between gender, transport and energy remain scant. Yet, as has been argued, 'decarbonisation of the transport sector and the introduction of new innovative technologies are not necessarily gender neutral. The high costs of the transition may hinder access to new technologies for the most vulnerable in society, who are disproportionately female' (Sansonetti & Davern, 2021).

Moreover, although the Energy-SHIFTS project aims were to help orient research into energy systems and transitions emerging from the context of the EU and to support the implementation of the SET-PLAN, many if not most of the priority research questions are seemingly relevant to various regional contexts, as shown by the research articles that were used to demonstrate the application of the GIA into Energy-SHIFTS. Most articles used (named in Tables 7-11, 13,14) report on empirical research carried out around the world: in Africa (Ethiopia, Kenya, Morocco, Niger Republic, Rwanda, South Africa, Tanzania), Asia/Southeast Asia (China, India, Vietnam), Europe (Finland, Germany,

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Norway, Poland, Sweden, UK), North America (US, Canada, Mexico), and South America (Colombia), and the Middle East (Iran).

Crucially, the GIA into Energy-SHIFTS application and demonstration exercise highlights that the gender-energy nexus has already been orienting research around the world. More importantly, it provides a compelling corrective to Energy-SHIFTS' missed opportunity to place gender at the forefront of research on energy systems and transitions and innovation. The scant attention paid to gender is all the more surprising, given that future research oriented by its priority questions is expected to play an effective role in helping achieve equality goals set out in development programs and policies in the EU, such as the SDG7 goals. Indeed, so far, only a tiny fragment (1%) of the available research literature on SDG7 (energy) includes considerations of sex and or gender issues (Herbert, Falk-Krzesinski, & Plume, 2020).

The GIA into Energy-SHIFTS exercise has shown that gender is not an explicit concern in most priority research questions. Yet, it has also shown how it can be usefully and meaningfully incorporated into many of the questions and illustrated with research conducted over the last few years that directly examine the variety of issues encompassed by the gender-energy nexus. This is an important outcome that, it is expected, can be replicated in other tasks in WP5 that entail the application of gender analysis to other remits. Task 5.3, for instance, entails the integration of gender perspectives into EUA recommendations for research, innovation, and education to achieve the mission of energy transition. Task 5.5, in turn, aims to integrate gender perspectives into the SDG7 targets to help promote gender sensitive research and innovation for SDGs and integration of gender perspectives in SDG implementation efforts. These tasks will contribute to the overarching aim of WP5 of identifying and reversing gender biases and gaps in the evidence, analytical methods and knowledge that shapes the discourse on equitable, just, and fair energy transition (gEneSys, 2024).

Clearly, gender remains to be mainstreamed into research on energy and energy transitions in the EU context, and likely elsewhere. Yet, the warning has been sounded to aspirations for gender equality that 'efforts to increase women's participation will not succeed without mainstreaming the methods of sex and gender analysis into knowledge production' (Schienbinger, 2014). The implementation of gender-sensitive research constitutes an urgent imperative if research is to help address and mitigate prevalent gender blindness and biases that thwart equal, just, fair, and sustainable access to, use of, management and governance of extant and emerging energy systems and technologies.

6. REFERENCES

- de Nicola, A., D'Agostino, G., Fresilli, B., Peri, V. M., Patriarca, T., Leonardi, N., . . . de Nicola, A. (2023). *D1.1 Systematic Literature Review of Studies at the Nexus of Gender Equality and Sustainable Energy Systems and Ontology of Energy Systems*. gEneSys.
- EC. (2024). *Strategic Energy Technology Plan*. Retrieved from https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/research-and-technology/strategic-energy-technology-plan_en
- Energy-SHIFTS. (2024). *Energy Shifts*. Retrieved from <https://energy-shifts.eu/>
- Foulds, C., Royston, S., Berker, T., Nakopoulou, E., Abram, S., Ancic, B., . . . Zivcic, L. (2020). *100 Social Sciences and Humanities Priority Research Questions for Energy Efficiency in Horizon Europe*. Cambridge: Energy-SHIFTS.
- gEneSys. (2024). *gEneSys*. Retrieved from How to: <https://www.genesys-project.eu/how-to/>
- GI. (2024). *Gendered Innovations*. Retrieved from Methods of Sex, Gender and Intersectional Analysis: <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/methods-sex-and-gender-analysis.html>
- Herbert, R., Falk-Krzesinski, H., & Plume, A. (2020). Sustainability Through a Gender Lens: The Extent to Which Research on UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Includes Sex and Gender Consideration. *SSRN*. doi:<https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3689205>
- Pollitzer, E. (2023). *D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy*. gEneSys.
- Robison, R., Skosvold, T. M., Lehne, J., Judson, E., Pechancova, V., Foulds, C., . . . Wyckmans, A. (2020). *100 Social Sciences and Humanities Priority Research Questions for Smart Consumption in Horizon Europe*. Cambridge: Energy-SHIFTS.
- Ryghaugh, M., Suboticki, I., von Wirth, T., Smeds, E., Scherrer, A., Foulds, C., . . . Wentland, A. (2020). *100 Social Sciences and Humanities Priority Research Questions for Transport and Mobility in Horizon Europe*. Cambridge: Energy-SHIFTS.
- Sansonetti, S., & Davern, E. (2021). *Women and Transport*. Brussels: Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs, European Parliament. Retrieved from [https://www.google.com/search?sca_esv=599099908&rlz=1C1GCEA_enGB1051GB1053&xsrf=ACQVn09ODLzWB3Vuym10yqZCCqXTpSARpw:1705492893656&q=https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_STU\(2021\)701004%23:~:text=3DThis%2520study%252C%2520+commissioned](https://www.google.com/search?sca_esv=599099908&rlz=1C1GCEA_enGB1051GB1053&xsrf=ACQVn09ODLzWB3Vuym10yqZCCqXTpSARpw:1705492893656&q=https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_STU(2021)701004%23:~:text=3DThis%2520study%252C%2520+commissioned)
- Schienbinger, L. (2014). Gendered innovations: harnessing the creative. *Triple Helix*, 1(9). doi:<http://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s40604-014-0009-7>
- Standal, K., Talevi, M., & Westskog, H. (2020). Engaging men and women in energy production in Norway and the United Kingdom: The significance of social practices and gender relations. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 60. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338>

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UN. (2024). *UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs - Sustainable Development*. Retrieved from Goals 7 Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal7>

von Wirth, T., Loorbach, D., Wagner, A., Koretskaya, O., Wade, R., Krupnik, S., . . . Zapletalova, V. (2020). *100 Social Sciences and Humanities Research Questions for Renewable Energy in Horizon Europe*. Cambridge: Energy-SHIFTS.

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